

Classification of Brain Tumor in MRI Images Based on Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract— Structural Magnetic Resonance Image (MRI) is a useful technique to examine the internal structure of the brain. MRI is widely used for brain tumor detection as it gives a clear picture of brain soft tissues. Brain tumor identification and classification is a critical and time-consuming task, generally performed by radiologists. Brain tumors of different sizes and shapes can occur in any person. Extraction of exact tumor region and analysis of minute differences is difficult for humans. Digital image processing methodologies like preprocessing, segmentation, and classification are useful to clinical experts for the proper diagnosis of brain tumor types. This paper focuses on current trends in brain tumor detection using MRI images. Analysis of various state-of-the-art machine learning and deep learning-based methods is given. Available datasets and challenges are discussed. This extensive survey will be helpful for future research to develop a better decision support system, beneficial to radiologists for accurate brain tumor diagnosis.

Keywords— Structural MRI, Brain Tumor Detection, Image Processing, Machine Learning, Image Segmentation, Feature Extraction

I. INTRODUCTION

A brain tumor is the growth of abnormal tissues inside the brain. It causes pressure in the skull region and affects the normal functioning of the brain. Brain tumors are classified as benign and malignant tumors. Benign tumors are noncancerous. Malignant tumors are cancerous tumors in which brain tissues split endlessly and can spread into surrounding tissues. Identification and classification of brain tumors into benign or malignant types is important for further treatment and survival of patients. Different medical image modalities like Computer Tomography (CT), Positron Emission Tomography (PET), and Magnetic Resonance Images (MRI) are used for brain tumor detection. MRI is a non-invasive technique that uses magnetic fields and radiofrequency pulses to depict the internal body structure. Three types of MRI sequences namely T1 weighted, T2 weighted, and FLAIR (Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery)

are used for brain tumor diagnosis.

Figure 1: T1 weighted, T2 weighted, and FLAIR MRI images

The identification and detection of tumor-infected areas from brain MRI is a critical task. Clinical experts examine medical images to identify signs and location of tumor. Due to the complex nature of MRI, there is a limitation for the human eye to analyze the minute differences. In recent years Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems are introduced by various authors to help radiologists with accurate diagnoses. This paper focuses on a review of various automatic brain tumor classification methods and highlights their strengths and limitations. Comparative analysis can be used as a new research aspect for developing better brain tumor segmentation and classification system.

A. Brain Tumor Detection Approaches

Machine learning algorithms for brain tumor detection incorporate four main stages namely Preprocessing, Segmentation, Feature Extraction, and Classification.

Figure 2. General block diagram of brain tumor classification

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Pre-processing: In the medical field, it is essential to get precise images for accurate observations of disease. The quality of medical images depends upon the sources of artifact acquisition such as MRI, PET, CT, etc. MRI scans may contain a lot of unwanted and irrelevant parts in their actual images. MRI is influenced by Rician noise.[33] Rician noise is signal-dependent and it is challenging to remove it. Image preprocessing techniques like filtering, contrast enhancement, and skull stripping are used to retain original image properties.

Segmentation: Segmentation is used to extract Region of Interest (ROI) from digital images. It is crucial to separate out the tumor region from the brain MRI. Different supervised and unsupervised techniques like thresholding, soft computing, atlas-based, clustering, neural network, etc. exist for segmentation. Thresholding includes adaptive, global, Otsu's, histogram-based thresholding methods. Unsupervised clustering techniques include K-means, and Fuzzy C means. It gives effective segmentation of brain MRI into Gray Matter (GM), White Matter (WM), and Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF). Segmentation is also performed using bio-inspired algorithms like Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [6], Genetic Algorithm (GA) [14]. The advances in segmentation show that deep learning architectures like CNN, Mask-RNN, and U-net give better performance over traditional methods.[21]

Feature Extraction: In feature extraction, various features like shape, texture, wavelet, and Gabor features are extracted from MRI. Gray-Level- Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) is used by most researchers. It is a second-order statistical method that can give texture features like energy, correlation, contrast, etc. [5]. The wavelet features are extracted using Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT). It is applied to raw images, approximation coefficients are extracted and selected as a feature vector.[19] It is observed that handcrafted features along with automatic features using deep learning models like CNN, ResNet, and Capsule network have shown good performance.[1]-[4]. Feature reduction is achieved using PCA, and GA [6]-[15].

Classification: Brain tumors are mainly classified as benign and malignant tumors. Malignant tumors are further divided into types Glioma, Meningioma, and Pituitary. WHO has given the grading of Glioma into 4 different grades as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Brain Tumor Types

B. Deep Learning Techniques

Deep learning is generally performed by a convolutional neural network which consists of the input layer, output layer, hidden layers, and hyperparameters. It is a supervised classification method in which the kernel convolves around input images to produce feature maps. DL is useful for automatic segmentation and feature extraction. Besides its popularity for medical disease diagnosis, it suffers from some disadvantages like the need to build complex architectures, tuning of hyperparameters, the need for a large amount of data for training, more training time, and cost. A recent study shows that to overcome the large data availability issue extensive data augmentation methods like rotation, cropping, scaling, and transformation are used. In transfer, learning methods pre-trained neural network is applied to the application-specific dataset to extract similar features [11]. Existing transfer learning models such as VGG19, LetNet, GoogleNet, ResNet, AlexNet are used for brain tumor detection. Figure 4 shows the architecture of LetNet5.

Figure 4: CNN LetNet5 Architecture [24]

Available Datasets: CAD systems developed for automatic brain tumor classification are evaluated on different publicly available databases. Brain Web simulated brain MRI database for the normal and abnormal brain is provided by McConnell Brain Imaging Centre. The Repository of Molecular Brain Neoplasia Data (REMBRANDT) containing pre-surgical multisequence MRI images of 130 patients is given by The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA). The database used for Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention (MICCAI) challenge is taken from the Section of Biomedical Image Analysis (SBIA) of the Center of Biomedical Image Computing and Analytics (CBICA) at the University of Pennsylvania. It is referred to Brain Tumor Segmentation (BraTS) dataset.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Brain tumor diagnosis using state-of-the-art machine learning algorithms and various machine learning methods are available for brain tumor segmentation and classification through MRI in the literature. Hasan et al. proposed a system for MRI brain scan classification using deep and handcrafted image features [1]. Pre-processed MRI is applied on modified GLCM for statistical feature extraction. Automatic feature extraction is done by CNN. SVM classification with 10-fold cross-validation has shown 99.30% accuracy on 600 axial MRI scans. The proposed method has shown good performance by combining MGLCM and CNN features when compared with other transfer learning networks like AlexNet, GoogleNet. A Naive Bayes-based brain tumor detection system uses threshold-based maximum entropy segmentation [3]. The system is checked on the REMBRANDT dataset containing 114 MRIs. The proposed method has the advantage that it can detect a tumor in all possible locations of the brain including the temporal lobe. A new approach for brain tumor diagnosis based on maximum fuzzy entropy segmentation and CNN is introduced in [4]. Single Image Super-Resolution is applied on MRI to increase the resolution. Features are extracted from pre-trained ResNet architecture. SVM Binary classification gives 95% accuracy. The mean shift clustering technique is used for segmentation in brain tumor classification using Edge Adaptive Total Variation [5]. The proposed method has two benefits, EADTV preserves edges while denoising the image, and mean-shift clustering updates cluster centers automatically unlike K-mean, fuzzy c- mean. An integrated design of PSO with fusion features for brain tumor detection uses a Local Binary Pattern and fine-tuned capsule network for feature extraction [6]. SVM classification gives an accuracy of 98.3% and 97.9% on the BRATS2018 and RIDER datasets. The proposed design has shown good results with the fusion of handcrafted and deep features. Pre-trained GoogleNet for deep feature extraction is evaluated on the CE- MRI dataset for 3 class classification

into Glioma, Meningioma, and Pituitary tumors using SVM and KNN classifiers with an accuracy of 97.8% and 98% respectively [7]. The brain tumor classification approach using a multinomial logistic regression model is evaluated on the BRATS 2017 dataset containing 48 images with 100% accuracy. However, the performance of the system should be verified on larger datasets [8]. An intelligent system for early assessment of brain tumor detection is suggested by Keerthana et al. [13]. Noise removal and skull stripping is followed by threshold-based segmentation. GLCM texture features are given to SVM for 3 class classifications normal, benign, and malignant tumors. The system gives good performance with the GA-SVM classifier. An efficient optimization technique for brain tumor classification uses GA for tumor segmentation. GLCM texture features are given to SVM with an accuracy of 91.23% [14]. Polly et al. presented a system for HGG and LGG brain tumor classification using k-means segmentation [15]. PCA is used to select 10 relevant features from wavelet features. SVM is used to identify normal and abnormal images. For abnormal images again SVM classifier is applied to classify HGG and LGG tumors. The proposed system shows 99% accuracy for 440 images however the system needs to be evaluated for a large dataset with more relevant features. A method for brain tumor detection using wavelet transform uses morphological operation with the threshold-based approach for segmentation [19]. Amin et al. presented a distinct approach for brain tumor detection using MRI [23]. Skull stripping and Gaussian filtering is applied to remove noise and smooth MRI. K-means segmentation is followed by GLCM texture features extraction. The system is evaluated on 3 datasets local, AANLIB, and RIDER with different SVM kernels linear, RBF, and cubic. It is observed that the linear kernel with 5-fold cross-validation has given 98% accuracy. A CAD system for brain tumor detection using Otsu thresholding is suggested in [25]. The customized Otsu method is applied on pre-processed MRI to obtain thresholds for normal and abnormal tissues. Feature vector consists of LBP, Gabor, Zeneka moments, and shape features. The proposed system has the advantage that the fusion of different features has given good accuracy over the separate feature sets. A decision support system for Glioma detection from brain MRI uses Dynamic Stochastic Resonance and Anisotropic Diffusion (DSR-AD) technique [26]. Texture features are extracted using the RLCP (Run length of centralized pattern) method. It has an advantage over other methods in that it preserves texture properties and can detect directional biasing of textual patterns. Naive Bayes classifier with 10 folds cross-validation has given classification accuracy of 96%. Please note that math equations might need to be reformatted from the original submission for page layout reasons. This includes the possibility that some in-line equations will be made to display equations to create a better flow in a paragraph. If display equations do not fit in the two-column format, they will also be reformatted. Authors are strongly encouraged to ensure that equations fit in the given column width. Median filtering noise elimination is followed by

threshold-based segmentation. The system proposes texture-based classification using GLCM features. Chicken Swarm Optimization (CSO) based brain tumor diagnosis method has given 99% accuracy using SVM with RBF kernel. MRI images are processed using global

thresholding and Otsu's Segmentation. In order to optimize the parameters of SVM, the CSO optimization algorithm is used. CSO technique is preferable to PO in terms of accuracy, robustness, and execution time. A summary of different state-of-the-art methods is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of brain tumor detection using ML

Ref	Preprocessing, Segmentation	Features	Classification	Dataset	Accuracy
[1]	Image resizing and enhancement	GLCM, CNN	SVM	Local-Iraqi center of research.	99.30%
[3]	Morphological operation, pixel subtraction, Maximum entropy threshold segmentation	Morphological, Intensity	Naive Bayes	REMBRANDT	94%
[4]	Single Image Super-Resolution for image enhancement Segmentation-Maximum fuzzy entropy(MFE)	ResNet deep features	SVM	TCIA	95%
[7]	Min-max normalization, Resize 224*224	GoogleNet deep features	SVM, KNN	CE-MRI	SVM-97.8% KNN-98%
[14]	Median filter GA segmentation	GLCM	SVM	Harvard MedicalDataset	91.23%
[15]	OTSU Binarization K-means clustering	DWT	SVM	BRATS 2013, BRATS 2017, Midas	99%
[23]	Skull stripping-BSE Gaussian filtering, K-Means segmentation	GLCM, Intensity, shape	SVM	Local, AANLIB, and RIDER	98%
[25]	Image enhancement-DSR-AD, OTSU segmentation	Tamura, LBP, GLCM, Gabor, Shape	SVM	Local	98%
[26]	Image enhancement-DSR-AD, Globaladaptive segmentation	RLCP	Naive Bayes	Local-JMCD, BRATS	96%

III. BRAIN TUMOR DIAGNOSIS USING DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHMS

Brain tumor detection using deep learning algorithms is an advanced field of research. Different deep learning architectures are used by researchers for the automatic segmentation and classification of brain tumors. Gumaei et al. suggested Regularized Extreme Learning Method with hybrid features for brain classification [2]. A Hybrid PCA-NGIST feature extractor is used for spatial feature extraction. NGIST is a normalized feature descriptor, used to resolve the problem of image illumination and shadowing. RELM is a feed-forward neural network with input, output, and a single hidden layer. The proposed method is tested for 3 class classifications Meningioma, Glioma, and Pituitary tumor on the CE-MRI dataset with an accuracy of 94.33% using 5-fold cross-validations. A light deep neural network architecture LinkNet is used for brain tumor classification in [9]. Binary classification has given 91% accuracy on the publically available UCI repository dataset. Mallick et al. presented brain MRI cancer detection technique using Deep

Wavelet Autoencoder based Deep Neural Network (DWA-DNN) [10]. DICOM images from the Rider dataset are processed to get a specific image matrix and passed to the Deep wavelet Autoencoder. Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) classification has given 96% accuracy and 0.65 Kappa statistics. However, in a future combination of DNN with other variations of autoencoder like denoising autoencoder, sparse autoencoder could be evaluated. A brain tumor classification system with a transfer learning method is proposed in [11]. MRI images are resized to 224*224 to fit the VGG19 model. Blockwise fine-tuning of parameters like learning rate, scheduling rate, and momentum is done to update the weights. The system is evaluated on the CE-MRI dataset with an accuracy of 94.82%. The system has the disadvantage that block-wise fine-tuning of parameters takes 20-30 minutes to train the CNN classifier. MLP is used for brain tumor classification using statistical and wavelet features [12]. The system is evaluated by considering statistical and DWT features separately and combined feature sets. The combined feature set has shown good performance with an accuracy of 96.73%. The system shows the robustness of classification for a large dataset containing

40,300 images. Glioma tumor detection with ANFIS classification uses Non-Sub Sampled Contourlet Transform image enhancement [16]. ANFIS is used for binary classification into normal and Glioma brain tumor types on the BRATS 2015 dataset. The system has the advantage that traditional classification algorithms like SVM and CNN give classification errors for low-intensity Glioma images however ANFIS works well for both high and low-intensity Glioma images. A deep neural network-based system for brain tumor classification is evaluated on 66 MRI images from the AANLIB dataset. Fuzzy C-mean clustering is used for MRI segmentation. PCA is used to select relevant feature sets from DWT features. 7 layers DNN architecture is used for 4 class classification into classes normal, Glioblastoma, Sarcoma, and Carcinoma tumors [17]. Raju et al. proposed a novel approach for brain tumor classification using Bayesian fuzzy clustering and HSC-based multi SVN [18]. Feature vector consists of information-theoretic, scatter, and wavelet features. The proposed method has 4 level classifications with Multi SVNN. Level 1 for normal and abnormal tumors, level 2 for edema tumors, level 3 for core tumors, and level 4 for advanced tumors. Weights in SVNN are optimized using the HCS algorithm which is the integration of Harmony search and Crow search algorithm. This approach has the advantage that Harmony search has less complexity and Crow search better converges to the global optimum in less time. Abdalla et al. presented a CAD system for brain tumor detection using ANN [20]. Feedforward neural network is tested on the AANLIB dataset containing 239 images with 99% accuracy using Haarlick texture features. A multigrade brain classification system using CNN is proposed in [21]. The tumor is segmented using InputCascadeCNN architecture. Data samples are increased by using extensive data augmentation techniques like rotation, flip, and emboss. The system is evaluated on the CE-MRI dataset with 94.58% accuracy using VGG19 architecture. The proposed system addresses the issue of inadequate MRI image availability by using extensive data augmentation methods. In the future CAD system for brain tumor grade classification using lightweight CNN, architecture could be developed for better performance. MRI-based brain tumor grade classification using CNN and GA is suggested in [22]. CNN with 5 convolution layers and 2 fully connected layers is used to classify tumors into 3 types Glioma, Meningioma, and Pituitary. CNN with 6 convolution layers and 2 fully connected layers used for four grades of Glioma classification. GA is used to choose the proper parameters of CNN to like no. of convolution layers, max-pooling layers, no of filters, size of filters, activation function, and learning rate. A novel approach for brain tumor classification using the neuro-fuzzy feature selection method is evaluated on the BRATS dataset with 10 fuzzy rules [24].

IV. ANALYSIS

Brain tumor segmentation and classification are very critical and generally done by expert radiologists. Machine

learning and deep learning methods can be used as decision support systems for radiologists. This study gives a summary of different state-of-the-art techniques for automatic brain tumor classification. MRI images are pre-processed using median, Gaussian, Wiener filter, histogram equalization, and skull stripping methods. Segmentation is categorized into 6 types: clustering-based, statistical methods, ANN, region-based, and threshold-based edge detection methods. K-means, fuzzy C-means clustering, and adaptive, global thresholding methods are commonly used by researchers. Segmentation using deep learning is an advanced technology through which proper extraction of tumor regions is achieved with greater accuracy [21]. Feature extraction is mostly performed by GLCM and DWT. GLCM gives texture features and DWT gives approximation coefficients as feature vectors. Automatic feature extraction is accomplished by deep learning architectures ResNet, and capsule network [4]-[6]. For dimensionality reduction, PCA and bio-inspired algorithms like PSO, and GA are used. Selecting the best features for accurate classification is a difficult task, hence hybrid approach combining different features is used for efficient classification. Classification is achieved using machine learning and deep learning algorithms. SVM with different kernels Linear, RBF, and Cubic is commonly used for binary classification. CNN along with transfer learning models like VGG19, ResNet has given good classification results. A combination of fuzzy system and ANN, ANFIS shows better performance for binary classification. Standard available databases used for CAD systems are discussed in Table 1. BRATS have commonly used a dataset containing T1, T2 weighted, and FLAIR images. However single database doesn't contain all types of tumors and grades for classification. Researchers have to combine the databases or need to collect MRIs from local hospitals. Hence the performance of different techniques can't be compared effectively as different data sources are used for evaluation. A standard database containing all tumor types needs to be developed, which can be used as a benchmark for further research.

CONCLUSION

Digital image processing methodologies like pre-processing, segmentation and classification are used to develop CAD systems for brain tumor detection through MRI images. This paper reviews the traditional machine learning and deep learning methods for brain tumor detection. Various research articles have been studied from standard journals and conferences and a detailed analysis of each paper is presented. This article gives an overview of standard available MRI datasets. Many machine learning and deep learning algorithms are utilized for classification however SVM has given good accuracy. SVM is used commonly for binary classification of brain tumor into normal and abnormal types. Reliability, accuracy, and computation time are the important factors for developing an automatic brain tumor detection system. This survey gives an analysis of

state-of-the-art methods and can be used in the future for developing efficient diagnosis systems for other brain-related disorders like dementia, stroke, Alzheimer's, and Parkinson's disease with different MRI image modalities.

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